

AUTOMATIC SCANSION OF SANSKRIT POETRY FOR AUTHORSHIP CRITERIA.

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Abstract

The article describes the development of a program, written in SNOBOL 4, which will scan Sanskrit verse. The resulting patterns of syllables, word breaks etc., are then analyzed by a second set of programs and a possible authorship test is suggested.

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0. *Introduction*

In the study of metre one is faced with a great deal of very detailed, systematic data. Line after line of poetry has to be carefully scrutinized letter by letter. The metrical weight of each syllable must be recorded. And this process must be repeated for at least several hundred verses before any representative sample is built up. Say each line has 20 syllables and we look at 300 lines. That makes 6000 decisions, and no research has even begun.

Once the scansions are done they must be examined for patterns, tendencies, recurrences etc. One might gather a certain amount of material as one scans, but for sure it would have to be gone over again. The prospect is daunting. However, this type of work is the very bread and butter of computer studies. Nothing could be more appropriate or more obvious than the use of a computer in metrical analysis.

0.1 *Text*

The text chosen for this project was the *Kumārasambhava* of Kālidāsa.¹ Chapters two and six are in the same metre, the *anuṣṭubh*, and combined give a sample of over three hundred lines, so they were chosen as the text-sample. The *anuṣṭubh* is the most common metre in Sanskrit literature. It is often used even in places where a westerner would expect to find prose, for example in law books and mathematical treatises. It is a flexible metre consisting of two identical lines, each having sixteen syllables. Within these sixteen, the two halves of eight syllables fall into a regular pattern:

x x x x v - - x / x x x x v - v x / / bis

where - means a heavy syllable, va light, and x a choice of either. The eight-syllable quarters of the verse are called *pādas* in Sanskrit. Because the *anuṣṭubh* is so common in Sanskrit literature the results of its analysis would be of broad interest.

It was further thought that if the verses analyzed showed any marked features attributable to the author, then they could be drawn into comparison with the later chapters of the same work (nine onwards) which are generally regarded, on stylistic grounds, as being by an inferior poet. The comparison could point to basic, measurable differences in the handling of the metre.

0.2 *Sequence*

In actual fact it was the scansion program which was developed first. It was tested and honed on a small sample of ten lines. When it was doing its duty a few sessions were spent typing the text onto cards as described in the next section.

There was a certain amount of proof reading and then a new set of data cards was prepared (section 2.4), and fed into the analysis programs (section 3) which had meanwhile been written.

The project is described in a logical, not chronological, sequence.

1. *Text Preparation*

The Sanskrit text had first to be put into a machine readable form.

1.1 *Transliteration*

The standard scheme of transliteration for the Sanskrit alphabet unfortunately includes diacritics not available on a card punch. So a new scheme had to be worked out which would be easy on the eye of the reader, but would also go half way towards meeting the demands of the program and the hardware.²

The following scheme was, after much thought and experiment, adopted:³

Transliteration

<i>Standard</i>	<i>Adopted</i>	<i>Standard</i>	<i>Adopted</i>	<i>Standard</i>	<i>Adopted</i>
<i>a</i>	A	<i>g</i>	G	<i>dh</i>	DH
<i>ā</i>	AA	<i>gh</i>	GH	<i>n</i>	N
<i>i</i>	I	<i>ñ</i>	.G	<i>p</i>	P
<i>ī</i>	II	<i>c</i>	C	<i>ph</i>	PH
<i>u</i>	U	<i>ch</i>	CH	<i>b</i>	B
<i>ū</i>	UU	<i>j</i>	J	<i>bh</i>	BH
<i>ṛ</i>	*R	<i>jh</i>	JH	<i>m</i>	M
<i>ṝ</i>	&R	<i>ñ̄</i>	.J	<i>y</i>	Y
<i>l̄</i>	*L	<i>t̄</i>	.T	<i>r</i>	R
<i>e</i>	E	<i>ṭh</i>	T#	<i>l</i>	L
<i>ai</i>	AI	<i>d̄</i>	.D	<i>v</i>	V
<i>o</i>	O	<i>ḍh</i>	D#	<i>ṣ̄</i>	Z
<i>au</i>	AU	<i>ṇ̄</i>	.N	<i>ṣ</i>	.S
<i>m̄</i>	.M	<i>t</i>	T	<i>s</i>	S
<i>h̄</i>	.H	<i>th</i>	TH	<i>h</i>	H
<i>k</i>	K	<i>d</i>	D		
<i>kh</i>	KH				

Some of the more awkward features were deliberate and necessary, and play their part in the running of the program. Even so, this system is readily readable after very little practice. In spite of the care taken in setting up the transliteration it was still impossible to avoid all ambiguities in the program statements. For example, it was necessary to include a couple of statements which would make sure that the aspirated consonants KH, GH, CH, JH, TH, DH, PH, and BH were read as single letters, not as K, H, etc.

The following is a sample of the text as it was typed onto cards, with the

standard transliteration for comparison:-

12/AB UDGHAATA.H PRA.NAVO YAASAA.M NYAAAYAIS TRIBHIR UDIIRA.NAM

12/AB udghātaḥ praṇavo yāsāṃ nyāyais tribhir udīraṇam

1.2 Compounds

When the verses were typed onto cards, markers for compound words were included. Sanskrit makes extensive and conscious use of compounds and so it is important to know which words are compounded together and what kind of compound they make. A basic distinction can be made between *nitya-samāsas* (permanent-compounds) and *anitya-samāsas* (impermanent-compounds). The former are compounds which stand for one particular object which is more specific than the words of the compound themselves can tell us. For example, a blackbird is not just any bird which is black, although that is strictly all that the words tell us. In addition it is a particular species. And similarly for compounds like mayfly, nightlife, pocketmoney, and so on. Not any fly in May is a mayfly, not all money in the pocket is pocket-money, etc. The point is that a particular nexus of words has become permanently associated with one referent.

In contrast to this, an *anitya-samāsa* means just what it says. The compound is merely an example of its last member, qualified by its preceding member. For example, a doorhandle is any handle for a door. A flowerpot is any pot for flowers.

The reason for keeping track of this distinction was that at a later stage the *nityas* could be treated first as a single word, then as two, and the difference observed.

Marking the compounds also makes it possible to say whether a caesura falls inside or outside a word - a feature which would be relevant when looking at the later chapters of the poem. The symbols used were:-

- for a *nitya-samāsa*, eg: VAAG-IIZAM (*vāgī'sam*)

/ for an *anitya-samāsa*, eg: JAGAD/YONIR

Where a compound involved a combination of two vowels into one at a junction, the division was taken as falling between the last consonant of the first word and the conjunct (*sandhi*) vowel.

For example:

DIVA+OKASA.H → DIV-AUKASA.H

KEVALA+AATMANE → KEVAL/AATMANE.

1.3 Enclitics

Enclitics are a feature of the verse which does have relevance for the metre, but is very difficult to pin down in any fully defined way, for Sanskrit. In essence, enclitics are to do with stress. Now Sanskrit certainly was spoken with a stress accent (*ictus*), but this was connected with the development of Sanskrit as a vernacular, as opposed to a scholarly and religious language. All the descriptions of Sanskrit accent as such describe the tone system (*svara*), dismissing stress as a later degeneration. Added to this is the fact that poetry, and especially high class poetry, is normally chanted or sung. This may be just on one note (*ekasruti*), but in any case, it does away with pure stress and complicates the situation as far as enclitics are concerned.⁴ A provisional list of enclitics was

drawn up and since only a few of these were at all common (*ca, api, iva, eva, etc.*), the problem was not serious. In the text they were marked simply with a comma. Thus:

RUDRAA.NAAM,API; AMOGHE,PI; ZA.MSAT,IIVA.

1.4 Line Numbers

Six spaces at the beginning of each half verse were devoted to its label. First the line number was typed in two spaces. This was followed by a slash, and then by the letters A,B,C, or D, representing the four *pādas* of the verse. So, for example, the first half of verse eighteen of chapter two would be labelled: 18/AB2.

1.5 Proof Reading

There were mistakes made in typing up the text, but happily not many, and these were easily spotted when the texts were put through the scansion program (see 2.5). A short piece of program was included to help with the grosser aspects of proof-reading. This simply counted the syllables. If there were not sixteen, it printed out a message saying so. An example of this can be seen at the end of the chapters, where a different metre is used.⁵ (See Figure 1.)

2. Scansion Program

The text, as described, formed the data input for a program which read each line and produced the verses, their scansion and certain other features. The program was written in SNOBOL 4 which is a language especially suited to this type of work involving characters and patterns. It lightened the work of programming enormously.

2.1 Letters

The first part of the program told the computer how to read. Happily, the Sanskrit alphabet is highly scientific in its arrangement. The letters naturally fall into phonetic groups; sonants, surds, aspirates, non-aspirates, vowels, semi-vowels, etc. These different groups were assigned to SNOBOL variables so that a Sanskrit text could be read and divided up into, among other things, words.

2.2 Syllables

The next major step was to identify syllables. For the purpose of this program the computer was told that a syllable was a string of letters consisting of some vowel(s) followed by some consonant(s). This is the reverse of the normal procedure of taking a syllable as a consonant followed by a vowel. It was chosen for economy in the program.⁶ As in Sanskrit grammar, the principle of *lāghava*, or economy, applies to programming.

2.3 Syllable Weight

The syllables, as they were picked off, were then examined to find their metrical significance. This is the heart of the whole program and it is simple. A vowel, like a musical note, is measured in time. It is long or short. A syllable, while largely dependent for its quality on the vowel in it, is not entirely so, and therefore in metrics one talks of the weight of a syllable, not its length. A syllable is heavy or light.

The laws of Sanskrit scansion, which are the same as for Greek, are succinctly stated by the grammarian Pāṇini in the following way:⁷

- a) A short vowel makes a light syllable;
- b) Before a conjunct consonant it makes a heavy syllable;
- c) A long vowel makes a heavy syllable too.⁸

a) and c) were already taken care of, since the vowels were separately defined as long or short. b) however, had to be uniquely defined. And, of course, it does not matter if the letters of the conjunct are separated by a space, a slash (*anitya-samāsa*), a hyphen (*nitya-samāsa*), or a comma (enclitic). This sort of pattern problem is easily dealt with in SNOBOL and a few statements sufficed to make it possible to recognize heavy syllables of the type b).⁹

With the criteria of syllable weight thus established, each syllable was inspected to see which pattern it contained. A record of the answer was marked in a variable.

It should be noted that this program scans any material in Sanskrit. This includes not just *anuṣṭubh*, but any metre. It thus raises the interesting possibility of investigating prose rhythms.

2.4 Encoding of Scansions

Interwoven with the above algorithm was another sequence of operations. Each syllable was inspected not only for metrical weight, but also to see whether there were any word beginnings, compounds or enclitics falling within the syllable. Now a new string of characters was composed, which consisted not of the text itself, but of its metrical and structural features in an encoded form, together of course with its reference number.

In these new encoded lines,

- ' = a light syllable
- = a heavy syllable
- A = an *Anitya-samāsa*
- N = a *Nitya-samāsa*
- E = an Enclitic

So, for example:

58/AB SA,HI DEVA.H PARA.M JYOTIS TAMA.H/PAARE PRATI.ST#ITAM

was encoded as:

58/AB 'E'*--*'-*--*'-A--*'-'-

These encoded lines were then transferred onto a set of punch cards and became the data for a new set of programs which analyzed these extracted features of the verse.

2.5 Data output

Figure 2 shows an example of the printout for the beginning of chapter two.

After the brief definition of terms the verse of poetry was printed. Properly spaced under the vowel of each syllable was printed the syllable weight. The last

syllable of a half-verse is heavy by position, and so was marked '='. After this came the scansion by itself, for quick inspection, together with its text reference. Then the encoding was shown, and finally all the compounds were extracted and listed, as well as the enclitics, to facilitate proof-reading.

3. *Analysis Programs: Questions*

At this point the picture suddenly broadens out. We have processed the text and extracted the information relating to metre. It remains, then, to ask questions about the scansions and devise the best ways of answering them. Wilhelm Ott in his work on Latin Hexameters has simply arranged his metrical information in several different indexes and left it at that.¹⁰ His materials remain as reference books, to which others apply their own questions. To a degree this must be the approach, because the data available will answer all questions about metre, and any one investigator has a specific question in mind. Also, of course, if the information is well arranged, then it happens that while perusing it one spots an anomaly of some sort and can be led from there.

3.1 *Approaches taken here*

Three different types of program were applied to the scansions, asking different questions.

3.2 *Word Beginnings*

One set of programs picked out the number of times a word began at each syllable position in the line, for a number of *ślokas* (verses) taken together. It was in this context that it became important whether a compound be regarded as *nitya* or *anitya*, that is, as one word or two. In Figure 3 the counts for the two chapters are taken together and *nitya-samāsas* have been counted as single words. These counts, in conjunction with the output for the chapters taken separately, were subjected to the chi square test and found to be samples from the same population.

3.3 *Percentage of light or heavy syllables in each position*

The general pattern of *anuṣṭubh* verse was outlined above (section 0.1). Now, in this pattern there are a number of undetermined syllables (x). In actual practice, the Sanskrit poets varied their *anuṣṭubh* rather more than the given scheme suggests, but the variations were not random. In particular, the first and third *pādas* had a set of allowed variants called *vipulās* (extensions). The normal *anuṣṭubh* is called *pathyā* (middle-of-the-road) by contrast. The object of the present program was to examine the frequency of these variants, and to search for any unrecorded ones.

In Figure 4 the table of counts for chapter two shows the number (also expressed as a percentage) of times a given syllable position contained a heavy or a light syllable. The same information is also given in graphic form. From this arrangement of the data we can see the likelihood of a syllable having a certain weight and the dominant pattern of the *pathyā anuṣṭubh* is clear. This program was put to further use and a series of graphs were generated for the lines in which a chosen syllable had a fixed weight. Ratios for the occurrence of the different *vipulās* were calculated.

3.4 *Statistics of half-pāda patterns*

This was the most elaborate of the three analysis programs written, and the

most useful. Its operation was as follows:

Each half-verse of sixteen syllables was subdivided into four groups of four syllables (half-*pādas*). These groups and their text-reference were stored. Each time the same pattern of four syllables occurred it was stored in the same place and a count was kept of the number of times this happened per pattern. Finally, the patterns and their frequencies were printed, followed by each pattern and its text references. The text references were in the form "line-number/half of line/chapter". (Eg., 18/AB 2 = Chapter 2, line 18, *pādas* A & B) Thus we are presented with a picture of all the patterns used in the chapters, and their frequencies.

Figure 5 shows the analysis for chapters 2 and 6 taken together. The remainder of the text references has been omitted.

With this program it was possible to investigate in detail the patterns occurring in the verses. A textual emendation was prompted on metrical grounds and later confirmed grammatically. The chi square test was applied to the distribution of patterns on the first and third half-*pādas* of the verses for the two chapters. The variation observed from expected values was insignificant. Thus we have no metrical evidence for believing these two chapters to be the product of more than one pen.

3.5 *Patterns including word starts*

The above program was modified so that the patterns would include the positions of word starts. *Nitya-samāsas* were counted as single words. As can be seen immediately in Figure 6, the distribution has spread considerably, especially in the freer half-*pādas*, one and three. This brought the frequencies below the threshold for using the chi square test, and to carry the investigation further more data must be prepared and run. However, even from what we do have, it seems likely that it will be possible on the basis of this analysis to establish a metrical profile of our author, Kālidāsa.

3.6 *Conclusion*

What we are looking for is a test which will enable us to characterize an author on metrical grounds - or at least give us some extra evidence if there are other reasons for making judgements about him. And in the last section (3.5) we arrived at a constellation of data which might well furnish us with such a test - namely, to compare the way authors combine the patterns in their metres with the endings (or beginnings) of words. Work is continuing and more verses are at present being prepared for machine reading."

In the process of arriving at this step several facts about the distribution of metrical patterns have already been thrown up and with the foundation that has been laid with the scansion program we can find out as much about the verse as we have imagination to ask questions and skill to devise programs to answer them.

This project has brought us by a new path close to the boundaries of what is known about the *pathyā* and *vipulā* set up; in this the speed and accuracy of the computer have made possible what has cost scholars valuable time in painstaking counting and summing. And because a computer program is not a result but a process, and an extremely quick one, as long as we have the original data we also have, in principle, its analysis. There is no problem of storage. All our data is ready for other questions, whereas manually gathered materials are usually redundant once the single conclusion sought has been drawn.

Notes

- {1} A. Scharfé, *Kālidāsa Lexicon*, Vol. I, part III (Bruges, 1958).
- {2} The opposite extreme from this would be to have a number for each letter and, having learned them all, to type out the entire text in number code. This would then involve a transliteration program to make the text available for non-number-reading Sanskritists.
- {3} It is partially derivative from van Nooten's scheme (B.A. van Nooten, 'A mechanical concordance for a Sanskrit work', *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 85 (1965), p.57), but several changes have been made and the rank number system discarded as no longer relevant. SNOBOL 4 can deal directly with characters.
- {4} Or maybe this should be looked upon as a simplification. If the characteristics of stress no longer show themselves, enclitics are irrelevant.
- {5} Chapter two ends with *Mālinī*; chapter six with *Kāmadatta + Mrgendramukha/Suvaktra/Acala*.
- {6} The vowels were collectively referred to by the variable name EVOWLS. The SNOBOL function BREAK will match a null string, but SPAN will not. So the characters were picked off in groups starting with a vowel.
- {7} Pāṇini: greatest Indian grammarian, c. 400 BC.
- {8} Pāṇini, *Aṣṭādhyāyī*. The rules are: 1.4.10 *Hrasvam laghu*; 1.4.11 *Sāmyoge guru*; 1.4.12 *Dirgham ca*.
- {9} It was noticeable that in the process of programming, whenever it was necessary to define some element uniquely, such as a letter, a certain type of aspirate (section 2.1), a syllable (2.2), and here a conjunct consonant, the final form of the statement always had a distinctly Pāṇinian ring to it. And of course, the actual decision on the weight of each syllable is precisely Pāṇinian.
- {10} Wilhelm Ott, *Materialien zum Metrik und Stilistik* (Tübingen, 1972-).
- {11} It is hoped that more detailed results concerning Sanskrit metre will appear in an oriental studies publication at some time in the future.

ALTA SA LALITA/YO, SID/BHRUU/LATAA/CAARU/Z*R, GGA, M
 THIS LINE DOESN'T HAVE 16 SYLLABLES

64/A
 LALITA/YO, SID/BHRUU/LATAA/CAA,
 RU/Z*R, GGA, M,

(Note the message and the fact that the program scans non-*aruṣṭubh* also.)

COMPUTER SCANSTION OF SANSKRIT POETRY

- 1) THE SANSKRIT ALPHABET IS TRANSLITERATED AS FOLLOWS: A, AA, I, II, U, UU, *R, &R, *L, E, AI, O, AU, .M, .H, K, KH, G, GH, .G, C, CH, J, JH, .J, .T, T#, .D, D#, .N, T, TH, D, DH, N, P, PH, B, BH, M, Y, R, L, V, Z, .S, S, H
- 2) '-' REPRESENTS A *nitya samasa*; '/' an *arbitrary samasa*.
- 3) A COMMA (,) MARKS THE BEGINNING OF AN ENCLITIC.

Figure 1 (cf.1.5)

TASMIN VIPRAK*RTAA, H KAALE TAARAKE, NA DIV-AUKASA, H
 TURAASAHA, M PURO-DHAAYA DHAAMA SVAAYA, M-BHUVVA, M YAYU, H
 TE, SAAM AAVIR-ABHUUD BRAHMAA PARIMLAANA/MUKHA/ZRIYAAM
 SARASAA, M SUPTA/PADMAANAA, M PRAATAR DIIDHITIMAN, IVA
 ATHA SARVASYA DHAATAARA, M TE SARVE SARVATO-MUKHAM
 VAAG-IIZA, M VAAGBHIR ARTHYAABHI, H PRA, NIPATY OPATASTHIRE

01/AB
 DIV-AUKASA, H,
 PURO-DHAAYA,
 SVAAYA, M-BHUVVA, M,
 AAVIR-ABHUUD,
 PARIMLAANA/MUKHA/ZRIYAAM
 02/AB
 SUPTA/PADMAANAA, M,
 DIIDHITIMAN, IVA,
 SARVATO-MUKHAM,
 03/AB
 SARVATO-MUKHAM,
 03/CD
 VAAG-IIZA, M,

Figure 2 (cf. 2.5)

Syllable No.	Heavy	(%)	Light	(%)	Syllable No.	Heavy	(%)	Light	(%)
1	66'	52.381	60	47.619	9	76	60.3175	50	39.6825
2	84	66.6667	42	33.3333	10	74	58.7302	52	41.2698
3	87	69.0476	39	30.9524	11	106	84.127	20	15.873
4	77	61.1111	49	38.8889	12	68	53.9683	58	46.0317
5	15	11.9048	111	88.0952	13		0.	126	100.
6	115	91.2698	11	8.73016	14	126	100.	0.	0.
7	116	92.0635	10	7.93651	15		0.	126	100.
8	90	71.4286	36	28.5714	16	126	100.	0.	0.

The Number of Half Slokas (x) is = 126

Percentage of Heavy Syllables per Position in 126 lines

1	*****	52.381%	*****
2	*****	66.6667%	*****
3	*****	69.0476%	*****
4	*****	61.1111%	*****
5	*****	11.9048%	*****
6	*****	91.2698%	*****
7	*****	92.0635%	*****
8	*****	71.4286%	*****
9	*****	60.3175%	*****
10	*****	58.7302%	*****
11	*****	84.127%	*****
12	*****	53.9683%	*****
13	*****	0%	*****
14	*****	100%	*****
15	*****	100%	*****
16	*****	100%	*****

Figure 4 (cf. 3.3)

Number of Word Beginnings at each Syllable Position

Syllable No.	Word Starts						
1	314	5	94	9	312	13	101
2	60	6	135	10	34	14	126
3	137	7	126	11	131	15	86
4	119	8	12	12	125	16	8

Figure 3 (cf.3.2.)

Percentage of Light Syllables per Position in 126 lines.

1	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
1	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
2	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
2	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
3	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
3	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
3	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
4	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
4	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
5	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
5	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
6	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
6	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
7	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
7	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
8	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
8	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
9	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
9	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
10	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
10	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
11	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
11	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
12	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
12	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
13	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
13	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
14	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
14	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
15	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
15	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
16	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****
16	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****	*****

Figure 4 (cont.)

NUMBERS OF PATTERNS IN EACH HALF PADA AND REFERENCES

Quarter of line:	1		2		3		4		
	Pat.	Freq.	Pat.	Freq.	Pat.	Freq.	Pat.	Freq.	
1	---'	25	-'---	1	---'	36	'--'	314	1
2	'--'	29	----	16	'--'	22			2
3	'--'	25	-''-	9	'--'	24			3
4	'--'	18	'--'	1	--''	30			4
5	--''	18	'---	273	'--'	21			5
6	'--'	15	''--	14	-'---	50			6
7	-'---	46			----	35			7
8	'--'	29			'--'	37			8
9	----	29			-'-'	37			9
10	-'-'	19			'---	22			10
11	'---	24							11
12	--'-	37							12

TEXT REFERENCES FOR PATTERNS.

Line Quarter 1

---	01/AB 2,02/AB 2,12/AB 2,15/CD 2,26/CD 2,31/CD 2,37/AB 2,40/CD 2,44/CD 2,50/CD 2,52/AB 2,52/CD 2,61/AB 2,11/AB 6,14/AB 6,20/AB 6,20/CD 6,34/AB 6,36/AB 6,39/CD 6,46/CD 6,55/AB 6,69/AB 6,76/CD 6,84/AB 6,
'--'	05/AB 2,06/AB 2,06/CD 2,09/CD 2,14/CD 2,18/CD 2,19/AB 2,22/CD 2,39/CD 2,10/CD 6,15/AB 6,15/CD 6,24/AB 6,25/AB 6,26/CD 6,27/CD 6,35/CD 6,37/AB 6,39/AB 6,40/CD 6,41/CD 6,44/CD 6,47/AB 6,49/AB 6,64/CD 6,66/AB 6,66/CD 6,75/AB 6,78/CD 6,
'--'	04/AB 2,05/CD 2,07/CD 2,15/AB 2,17/CD 2,32/CD 2,35/CD 2,38/CD 2,55/AB 2,07/CD 6,08/CD 6,09/CD 6,17/CD 6,31/CD 6,34/CD 6,52/AB 6,54/CD 6,57/AB 6,60/AB 6,62/AB 6,67/CD 6,69/CD 6,71/CD 6,73/CD 6,82/AB 6,
'--'	09/AB 2,16/CD 2,17/AB 2,22/AB 2,29/CD 2,32/AB 2,56/CD 2,62/CD 2,02/AB 6,13/CD 6,51/CD 6,52/CD 6,56/CD 6,59/CD 6,77/CD 6,79/CD 6,82/CD 6,86/CD 6,
--''	13/CD 2,21/AB 2,21/CD 2,26/AB 2,30/CD 2,35/AB 2,41/AB 2,11/CD 6,23/AB 6,42/AB 6,46/AB 6,48/AB 6,55/CD 6,56/AB 6,60/CD 6,63/AB 6,84/CD 6,85/CD 6,
'--'	04/CD 2,08/AB 2,23/AB 2,24/AB 2,38/AB 2,53/AB 2,22/CD 6,35/AB 6,38/CD 6,65/AB 6,74/AB 6,78/AB 6,79/AB 6,81/AB 6,89/CD 6,
-'---	12/CD 2,14/AB 2,18/AB 2,25/CD 2,30/AB 2,39/AB 2,40/AB 2,46/AB 2,46/CD 2,48/CD 2,51/CD 2,53/CD 2,57/AB 2,63/AB 2,04/AB 6,05/AB 6,09/AB 6,10/AB 6,12/CD 6,16/CD 6,18/CD 6,19/AB 6,19/CD 6,21/CD 6,24/CD 6,29/CD 6,30/AB 6,33/AB 6,41/AB 6,44/AB 6,45/CD 6,51/AB 6,53/AB 6,53/CD 6,57/CD 6,58/AB 6,63/CD 6,68/AB 6,76/AB 6,77/AB 6,80/CD 6,88/AB 6,90/AB 6,91/AB 6,91/CD 6,93/CD 6,
'--'	02/CD 2,03/AB 2,16/AB 2,20/AB 2,23/CD 2,27/CD 2,28/CD 2,37/CD 2,45/AB 2,49/CD 2,55/CD 2,58/AB 2,63/CD 2,01/AB 6,03/AB 6,23/CD 6,25/CD 6,26/AB 6,28/AB 6,40/AB 6,43/CD 6,48/CD 6,50/CD 6,54/AB 6,62/CD 6,65/CD 6,70/CD 6,81/CD 6,87/AB 6,
----	03/CD 2,07/AB 2,11/CD 2,24/CD 2,34/AB 2,34/CD 2,44/AB 2,47/AB 2,60/CD 2,01/CD 6,06/AB 6,21/AB 6,22/AB 6,27/AB 6,31/AB 6,32/CD 6,37/CD 6,38/AB 6,49/CD 6,50/AB 6,61/AB 6,61/CD 6,67/AB 6,73/AB 6,80/AB 6,83/AB 6,85/AB 6,86/AB 6,94/CD 6,
-'-'	10/CD 2,33/CD 2,42/AB 2,42/CD 2,47/CD 2,61/CD 2,02/CD 6,12/AB 6,18/AB 6,30/CD 6,42/CD 6,68/CD 6,71/AB 6,72/AB 6,74/CD 6,75/CD 6,87/CD 6,88/CD 6,94/AB 6,
'---	01/CD 2,11/AB 2,19/CD 2,29/AB 2,33/AB 2,41/CD 2,45/CD 2,49/AB 2,50/AB 2,51/AB 2,56/AB 2,58/CD 2,59/AB 2,60/AB 2,62/AB 2,03/CD 6,07/AB 6,17/AB 6,33/CD 6,58/CD 6,59/AB 6,70/AB 6,83/CD 6,92/CD 6,
--'-	08/CD 2,10/AB 2,13/AB 2,20/CD 2,25/AB 2,27/AB 2,28/AB 2,31/AB 2,36/AB 2,36/CD 2,43/AB 2,43/CD 2,48/AB 2,54/AB 2,54/CD 2,57/CD 2,59/CD 2,04/CD 6,05/CD 6,06/CD 6,08/AB 6,13/AB 6,14/CD 6,16/AB 6,28/CD 6,29/AB 6,32/AB 6,36/CD 6,43/AB 6,45/AB 6,47/CD 6,64/AB 6,72/CD 6,89/AB 6,90/CD 6,92/AB 6,93/AB 6,

NUMBER OF PATTERNS IN EACH HALF PADA AND REFERENCES

Quarters of line	Pat. 1	Freq.	Pat. 2	Freq.	Pat. 3	Freq.	Pat. 4	Freq.	
1	-*-!*-	3	'-*--	46	*'-!*'!	4	*'-!*-	4	1
2	'!-'	2	*'*-*--	2	*--!*'!	6	'-*!*-	3	2
3	'-*!*-	1	'*-*--	7	*'-!'	1	'!-'	13	3
4	'*-*!*'	1	*'*-*-*	1	*'-!*-	2	*'*-!*-	1	4
5	'!*-!'	5	-*!'-	2	*-!-'	8	'!*-!'	64	5
6	'!*---	7	*'!'-	2	*-*--*-	1	*'-!'	31	6
7	'!-'	2	'*!'-	5	*'!*-*-!	2	*'-*!'-	17	7
8	--*-'	8	*'!*!*'-	1	*'!*-*--	2	'!*-*!'-	2	8
9	-*!-'	3	**-*!*'-	1	*--	1			9
10	--*--	7	*-*!*'-	1	*'!'-	2	'!*-!'	34	10
11	-*!'-	1	*'-*--	30	**--*-'	1			11
12	-*-'	7	*-'*'-	1	*-*!*-!	4	*'!*-!'	12	12
13	-*-'*'	1	'*--*	5	*'!*'-	1	'!*-!*-	3	13
14	--!'	1	*-'!'-	1	*'!*-**-	1	'!'-*'-	4	14
15	-*-'!	1	'--*--	4	*-*!-'	1			15
16	'!*-!'	2	*-'*--	1	*--!'	1			16
17	'!*-!'	2	*'!*-**--	1	*-*!'-	1			17
18	'!--!	1	*'!--*--	5	*'!*-*!'	5			18
19	'!*!'	2	-*--*--	1	*--*!'	8			19
20	'! ! ! !	1	*'!!*-*--	1	*-'!'-	7			20
21	--*--	1	'*--	39	*'!*'-*!'	1			21
22	--*-*!'	1	*'!*--	10	**-'!*-!	1			22
23	'!*-!'	5	*'!'-	10	*-*!*'-	2			23
24	--*!'	7	-*--	5					24
25	'!*-!'	3	'!--	8	*--*!*'	2			25
26	--*!'	1	'! ! !	1	*--*-'	5			26
27	--*!*'-	1	*'!'-*--	1	*--!*-	7			27
28	'!*! ! !	1			*'!*-*	4			28
29	'!*!*--	1			*'!*-!'	6			29
30	-!*-*	4			*'!*'-*--	1			30
31	'!'-*!'	7			*-'!*--	9			31
32	--*!*--	2			*'!!*-'	8			32
33	-!*!*--	1			*-'!*-'	3			33
34	'!'-*--	5			*--*-*--	3			34
35	-!'-*!'	4			*'!*-**--	1			35
36	--*!*-'	1			*'!!*--	9			36
37	'!*-*-'	1			*-'!*-*--	3			37
38	'!*-*!'	1			*--*-*!'	2			38
39	-!--	3			*-'!*-*!'	1			39
40	'!*--*--	1			*'!'-!	2			40
41	'!--*!'	2			*--*-*!'	6			41
42	-*-*-*--	1			*'!'-*--	2			42
43	---*--	3			*'!'-*!'	5			43
44	'!*-*--	3			*--*-*--	3			44
45	'!*-*!'	2			*-*-'*!'	1			45
46	'!'-	5			*'!*-!'	2			46
47	--*--	2			*-*-*-*--	1			47
48	'!*-'*--	2			*'!!*-*--	1			48
49	--!*-	5			*-'!*-*	9			49
50	'!'-*--	4			*'!'-!	2			50
51	'!'-*!'	2			*'!'-*!'	6			51
52	--!*!'	1			*-'!*-!	9			52
53	--*-*--	5			*-*--*!'	4			53

Figure 6 (cf. 3.5)

NUMBER OF PATTERNS IN EACH HALF PADA AND REFERENCES (contd)

54	- '*-'	6	*---'	1	54
55	-*'--*	6	*' *-' *'	1	55
56	--'--	3	*' '-*-	5	56
57	- '*--	10	*' ---	1	57
58	' '*-'	8	*' *--*'	1	58
59	' *---	1	*--*--'	2	59
60	-*--'	1	- '*--	1	60
61	' '*--	2			61
62	-**--'	1			62
63	-*---	1			63
64	- '*-*--	4			64
65	' *--'	1			65
66	' *'-' *'	1			66
67	-*--*'	1			67

TEXT REFERENCES FOR PATTERNS

Line Quarter 1

-*-'*-	06/CD 6,16/AB 6,29/AB 6,
' '-'	40/CD 6,66/AB 6,
'-*'*-	73/CD 6,
'*-'*'	79/AB 6,
'-*-'	02/AB 6,51/CD 6,59/CD 6,82/CD 6,86/CD 6,
'*--	03/CD 6,07/AB 6,33/CD 6,58/AB 6,59/AB 6,83/CD 6,92/CD 6,
' '-	09/CD 6,17/CD 6,
--*-'	11/AB 6,14/AB 6,20/CD 6,34/AB 6,39/CD 6,55/AB 6,69/AB 6,84/AB 6,
-*'-'	12/AB 6,68/CD 6,94/AB 6,
--*--	22/AB 6,31/AB 6,32/CD 6,38/AB 6,80/AB 6,85/AB 6,94/CD 6,
-*'--	68/AB 6,
-*-'-	13/AB 6,14/CD 6,43/AB 6,45/AB 6,47/CD 6,64/AB 6,92/AB 6,
-*-'*'	23/AB 6,
--' '	46/AB 6,
-*-' '	48/AB 6,
'*-'-	60/AB 6,67/CD 6,
'*-' '	65/AB 6,74/AB 6,
'--'	77/CD 6,
' '*''	95/A 6,95/D 6,
' '''	95/B 6,
-*-*--	21/AB 6,
-*-*'-	32/AB 6,
'-*'-	08/CD 6,31/CD 6,34/CD 6,52/AB 6,82/AB 6,
--*''	11/CD 6,42/AB 6,55/CD 6,56/AB 6,60/CD 6,63/AB 6,84/CD 6,
'-*''	35/AB 6,38/CD 6,89/CD 6,
--*'-	72/CD 6,
-**'-*-	93/CD 6,
'*'''	95/C 6,
'*''--	03/AB 6,
-'-*-	05/AB 6,58/AB 6,77/AB 6,80/CD 6,
' '-*'	10/CD 6,15/AB 6,35/CD 6,37/AB 6,49/AB 6,66/CD 6,78/CD 6,
-*' *--	16/CD 6,21/CD 6,
- '*--	19/CD 6,
' '-*-	26/AB 6,50/CD 6,54/AB 6,65/CD 6,81/CD 6,
-'-*'	42/CD 6,74/CD 6,87/CD 6,88/CD 6,
--**-'	46/CD 6,
'*--*'	52/CD 6,
'*--*'	78/AB 6,

Figure 6 (cont.)